

MEUS: a framework for Management of Emergencies through Ubiquitous Sensing

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Abstract—This paper models a scenario in which agents, that can be seen as First Responders, smart devices and/or robots explore the environment and exchange information in an emergency situation, i.e., after an earthquake, assessing damages, and searching for people needing assistance. While moving, the agents observe events and exchange the information collected with other agents encountered, thanks to common network connections. When some conditions hold, the agents can upload the collected information to a Control Room/database in the Cloud. The model includes a detailed description of how data are exchanged between agents and stored in the database. A simulated experiment has been carried out in a real-world street network, with the aim of evaluating the feasibility and performances of the approach.

Index Terms—Information Crowdsourcing, Distributed Sensing, Search and Rescue, Human-in-the-Loop.

I. INTRODUCTION

When it comes to handle the aftermath of a natural disaster in a Search and Rescue scenario, we have to deal with many and different types of agents: citizens affected by the disaster, First Responders and possibly drones and surveillance cameras. Moreover, the amount of data First Responders need to grapple with can be consistent and so slow down and hamper the search and rescue operations. The aim is to best manage the rescue mission by coordinating the First Responders' actions and prioritizing different situations of peril in which citizens might be involved in. We believe the problem can be tackled by means of an information crowdsourcing approach by endowing agents with an application (on their smartphones) and whenever they observe a relevant event (e.g., a man trapped in a house) they may wish to upload the information to the central database. This could be done either by using the app on their smartphone (if 4G connectivity is available), or by interacting with a First Responder patrolling the area (either verbally or through ad hoc, short-range communication, i.e., Bluetooth), who will then update the database accordingly. The main problem which arises from this scenario is the reliability of an information, which can be distorted and mislead First Responders and ultimately hinder the rescue operations. To take into account this issue each agent has a certain score of trustworthiness which gets updated dynamically, by means of a consensus algorithm, as new informations are reported in the database. The problem described prompts the need

for a proper simulator which can be leveraged to carry out meaningful tests. Hereafter we present a versatile framework which enable to simulate the context described in different cities and settings which can be exploited to validate different experiments as well as give a good insight about the scalability of the approach. The problem of Information Crowdsourcing and related standards has been addressed, e.g. to collect the need of people after or during a wildfire, an earthquake, or a flood [1] [2] [3] [4] [5] [6] [7] and check their quality [8] [9]. However, all these systems are based on usual messaging apps such as Twitter and Whatsapp, and work on a complete different time and spatial scale, in the order of days and across whole countries or regions.

II. DATA MANAGEMENT

A. Data Format

Some of the agents in the environment are equipped with network devices providing them with the capability to share information with a Control Room and/or on the Cloud, and are referred to as “gateway agents”; other agents are only able to communicate locally, i.e., with other agents within communication range (which, in turn, may behave as a gateways’).

As the system evolves, many different observations are stored in the agent’s local database.

Concerning data collection and storage, we propose a model which could enable us to easily reconstruct the graph for each observation made in the environment.

To achieve the aforementioned objective, the agents’ local database has been organized into what we defined as “Information Element” (IE). Through a Context-Free Grammar, the Information Element has been modeled as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} IE_i &\rightarrow O_i | IE_i J_{ij} \\ O_i &\rightarrow (A_i, \chi_k(t), t) \\ J_{ij} &\rightarrow (A_i, A_j, \chi_k(t), t) \end{aligned}$$

where:

- Observation O_i is made by an agent A_i that can be uniquely defined as a 3-tuple containing:
 - A_i : the agent that performed the observation;

- $\chi_k(t)$: the id of the node in which the observation made from agent A_i has occurred at time t ;
- t : the time in which the observation has occurred.
- Jump J_{ij} is a 4-tuple containing the information related to an exchange of the Observation:
 - A_i : the teller agent;
 - A_j : the listener agent;
 - $\chi_k(t)$: the id of the node in which the information exchange has occurred between agents A_i and A_j ;
 - t : the time when information exchange occurred.

It cannot happen that the same observation is exchanged multiple times between the same agents at different times.

III. SIMULATED EXPERIMENTS

A. Simulation

The simulator is implemented in Python, exploiting OSMnx: a Python package meant to download spatial data from OpenStreetMap with real-world street networks.

Coherently with the model, each graph node contains the following relevant information: (i) position in the environment expressed both in Latitude and Longitude and in UTM coordinates; (ii) event that can be observed in that node described as a tuple (Situation, Object); (iii) Internet connection coverage availability. The remote database to store Information Elements is implemented as a relational database in the Cloud using Flask-RESTful (an extension for Flask that adds support for building REST APIs), Marshmallow and SQLAlchemy.

B. Experimental results

Preliminary experiments have been carried out, exploiting the map of the city of Amatrice, by varying the following relevant parameters:

- 1) the ratio of agents that are equipped not only with a local network connection but have also a global connection, i.e., percentage of the total 100 agents which are gateways and that can upload data to the remote database;
- 2) the radius amplitude of the global connection coverage.

Fig. 1. latency (intended to be the number of loops required for an event to be uploaded on the remote database by an agent) vs. number of gateways relationship.

Fig. 2. latency vs. amplitude of the radius for the global connection coverage relationship.

The conclusion from the above figures 1 and 2 is two-fold:

- 1) Varying the percentage of gateways' agents, as the number increases the number of loops required to report the same number of observations decreases.
- 2) Increasing the radius of the internet connection coverage, again, the number of loops required to report the same number of observations decreases.

This gives space for further exploration of different aspects of the scenario such as the consensus approach to compute the reliability of each agent.

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